

Meditation in Context of Different Religions

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Abstract

Meditation is a practice that mainly involve of focusing or clearing the mind through combination of mental and physical techniques. Depending on the goal of meditation it can be of different types. Some people practice this for attaining mental health, and some of them practice it for spiritual growth. As we know there are many religions in the world and the meditation practices vary from one religion to other, but the main motive of every religion and the meditation practices they have is to attain the mental and spiritual well-being. There is no restriction or limitation on the practices of meditation on the name of religion. It can be performed by any person belonging to different religious practices. Only the method of meditation is varied from one religion to other, but aim of all practices is to attain mental peace and happiness in life. As we know in meditation, we only focus on raising our consciousness to the next level where we have clear and positive thought process. And we became aware of things around us.

Key words: Different Religion, Meditation.

Introduction

The word meditation came from Latin word *meditatum* which means to contemplate. To determine the exact origin of meditation is difficult but almost it has been practised for thousands of years as a spiritual conduct. We can find the written records of meditation in Hindu Vedantism around 1500 BCE. Because archaeologist have found the images which shows the meditative posture with sitting on ground with cross legged.

Hinduism

Dhyana in Hinduism is means for meditation or contemplation. Dhayana is given in the Yogic practices and it is a means to attain Samadhi and self-knowledge. The term meditation is given in the Hindu scripture like Vedas, Upanishads and Srimad Bhagwat geeta. (htt). In Hinduism the aim of the meditation is mainly to attain Moksha or the union of one self to the Brahman. Different techniques are adopted by Hindu to practice meditation like chosen image, repeating mantras, chanting, on breath (pranayama) etc. There is ethical discipline like yamas, niyama, asana, pranayama, dharana (one pointed concentration of mind) is given to practice before stepping towards meditation. In Upanishads, the meditation practice has three aspects which is hearing, reflection, and meditation. (Ubeysekara, 6 august,2016).

Jainism

Scripture of Jain offer extensive techniques for meditation to gain full awareness and knowledge. One of the most pleasant, joyous feelings is meditation. Because when we meditate, we maintain our focus on one thought which makes us more concentrated and gives us tremendous energy. one of the oldest Agam of Jainism is Aayaro which defines meditation as one who meditate got to know the reality of

body every moment. The main aim of Jain meditation is to remove the Rag and Dwesh, keeping samta (equanimity) and full awareness through meditation. (Jain, n.d.). according to Jainism meditation is of supreme power for achieving the concentration of mind and the liberation of the soul. There are four types of meditation given in Jainism – Arta (sorrowful meditation), Raudra (inclement meditation), dharmya (righteous meditation) and sukla (spiritual meditation). The first two gives us pain and sorrow, but the other two are useful for removing the bondage of worldly things and all the desires. Jaina also follows the four stages of self – discipline which is pratyahara, dharana, dhyana and Samadhi. The main purpose of meditation is to complete removal of all karmas. (Jain P. P.).

Buddhism

There are several schools of Buddhism, and the main are two – Theravada tradition – which is also known as teaching of elders. And the second is Mahayana tradition, in this branch there is subdivision like Tibetan, Zen etc. the central place in Buddhism is occupied by meditation and in its highest stage it connects with the wisdom. There are four stages given in dhyana practices which shift from outer world to inner self. (1) detachment from the outer world. (2) concentration without any investigation. (3) passing away from the joy with left ease. (4) the passing of ease with left of self-possession. (Bhutia, 2017). Buddhist meditation is the collection of methods which are mainly designed to gives the deeper understanding of self and the nature of reality. The main method includes like focusing on breath, observing our thoughts, and developing kindness. There are many types of meditation techniques in Buddhism but three are core to this.

1. Samatha (Concentration Meditation)

This meditation is mainly for beginners to perform which include focusing on a singular object like breath, mantra, visual object. All these develop great concentration and deep state of calm mind.

2. Vipassana (Insight Meditation)

This practice is higher stage of Samatha meditation. In this meditation one has to observe the whole body, thoughts and feelings with clear awareness.

3. Matta Bhavana (Loving- Kindness Meditation)

Above two practices mainly focus on personal insight, but in this practice, we connect ourself to other with love and compassion.

In Buddhism meditation means careful attention toward ones all internal and external experiences. (Wynme, 2007).

Islam

In Islam meditation is the core of spirituality, but it not gets the attention and focus which it deserves. Meditation means surrendering everything in conscious state of mind to the Allah. There is different form of meditation in Islam which enhance their physical act of worship, fasting and dhikr. All the practice of meditation in Islam involve to surrender and remembering Allah. And all this lead to purify our heart and mind from evil thought and feelings. (Shah, 2023). There is diverse meditation practice in Islam which depend on the element of ritual prayer. There is no single word use as meditation but the process of prayer. The central practice of Sufism is meditation which considered as mental approach from this worldly life to divine.

Dhikr - Which means remembrance of God and repeating the phrases of Quran.

Muraqaba - Focusing mainly on the presence of God. Which means contemplation.

Sama - It is more embodied practice which involves music and motion of the body as meditative tool. (Kugle, 2021).

Christianity

The concept of meditation has come several times in the Bible. There are four stages of Christian meditation – reading, discursive meditation, affective prayer and contemplation. It is believed that spending time with God means enhancing relationship with God and making life better. A method given by John Main which involve repeating a sacred mantra “Maranatha” means come Lord Jesus.

Sikhism

The main goal of meditation is to attained higher state of consciousness. The Gurmukh is one who attains the fourth higher state of consciousness. To get this level one have to leave behind all the worldly things and interact with higher consciousness. (Sikhi Wiki, 2012). Meditation is also known as timeless science and it is medicine for soul. Meditation is core practice for many of shikh followers. They believe that meditation helps in clearing the mind through which they can see our own soul and the god within. The simplest form of meditation is to sit quietly and start chanting mantra. Sikhs believe that when they meditate on mantra all the thoughts, all ambition which are flowing in a negative direction, starts to flow in positive direction. (khalsa, 1994).

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